

SCALE DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF GENDER DISPARITY AND LEARNING ACHIEVEMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION: A CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to develop and validate a comprehensive scale measuring gender disparity and learning achievement in higher education. Conducted at a public sector university in Punjab, Pakistan, the study focused on BS (4-year) students from the Faculty of Social Sciences. Using proportionate random sampling, a total of 316 students were selected, with sample sizes proportionally allocated to each department. A cross-sectional survey was administered through a structured questionnaire, designed to assess multiple dimensions, including gender disparity in enrolment, classroom participation, learning environment, communication, residential background, access to resources, flexible instructional methods, supportive classroom climate, collaborative learning opportunities, equitable assessment methods, policy and institutional support, and culturally relevant teaching materials. Each variable consisted of eight items, resulting in a 96-item scale. The tool was pre-tested with 30 randomly selected students using a Likert-type scale, and reliability was confirmed with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.939. Confirmatory factor analysis was conducted to validate the structure and factors of the scale. The study concludes that the validated instrument is psychometrically sound and capable of accurately capturing gender disparities and their impact on learning achievement. The findings offer actionable insights for educators, administrators, and policymakers to identify inequities, implement targeted interventions, and promote equitable learning opportunities. This scale provides a robust tool to support evidence-based strategies aimed at reducing gender disparities and enhancing academic outcomes for all higher education students.

Keywords: Scale Development, Gender Disparity, Learning Achievement, Higher Education, Confirmatory Factor Analysis

INTRODUCTION

Gender disparity in higher education remains a critical concern worldwide, affecting students' access to learning opportunities, engagement in academic activities, and overall learning achievement (Seguino, 2002; Shoaib & Zaman, 2025; Shoaib, Zaman, & Abdullah, 2025).

Despite considerable progress in promoting gender equality, male and female students often experience differences in enrolment patterns, classroom participation, access to resources, and academic performance (Assarsson, Petersen, Hogberg, Strandh, & Johansson,

2018; Shoaib, Waris, & Iqbal, 2025b, 2025c). Understanding and measuring these disparities is essential for developing effective policies and interventions that promote equitable learning outcomes across genders (Kamenou, 2020; Shoaib, Waris, & Iqbal, 2025a; Shoaib, Waris, & Iqbal, 2025b). Accurate measurement of gender disparity and its impact on learning achievement requires reliable and valid assessment tools (Morgan, Williams, & Gott, 2017; Shoaib & Ullah, 2025; Shoaib, Waris, & Iqbal, 2025a). Existing studies often rely on descriptive or comparative methods, but few provide psychometrically sound instruments that quantify the complex relationship between gender differences and academic outcomes in higher education (Morley & Crossouard, 2016; Shoaib, Tariq, & Iqbal, 2025b; Shoaib, Tariq, Rasool, & Iqbal, 2025). Developing a standardized scale enables researchers and educators to systematically assess disparities, identify contributing factors, and evaluate interventions aimed at reducing inequities in learning achievement (Johnson, Warr, Hegarty, & Guillemin, 2015; Shoaib, Shamsher, & Iqbal, 2025; Shoaib, Tariq, & Iqbal, 2025a). Scale development involves the careful construction of items that represent theoretical constructs, followed by rigorous testing to ensure validity and reliability. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is a statistical technique commonly used to validate the structure of a scale, confirm the relationships between observed variables and underlying constructs, and ensure that the instrument accurately measures the intended dimensions (Shoaib, Rasool, Zaman, & Ahmed, 2025; Shoaib, Shamsher, & Iqbal, 2025). By applying CFA, researchers establish the psychometric soundness of the scale, thereby enhancing its utility in both research and practice. The present study, “scale development and validation of gender disparity and learning achievement in higher education: a confirmatory factor analysis,” seeks to create and validate a reliable instrument for assessing gender-related differences in learning achievement. The study aims to provide a robust tool for educators, policymakers, and researchers to evaluate gender disparities, understand their influence on academic performance, and design strategies to foster

equitable learning environments in higher education institutions. This research contributes to the field by combining rigorous scale development methodology with advanced statistical validation, ensuring that the resulting instrument is both theoretically sound and practically applicable.

Study Context

Higher education institutions are increasingly diverse, enrolling students from different cultural, social, and educational backgrounds (Shoaib, Rasool, & Zaman, 2025c; Shoaib, Rasool, Zaman, & Abdullah, 2025). Despite efforts to promote gender equality, disparities persist in various aspects of the academic experience, including enrolment, classroom participation, access to learning resources, and ultimately, learning achievement (Shoaib, Rasool, & Zaman, 2025a, 2025b). These differences are often influenced by broader societal norms, institutional practices, and classroom dynamics, making it essential to systematically measure and understand the impact of gender on academic outcomes (Shoaib, Rasool, Iqbal, & Abdullah, 2025b; Shoaib, Rasool, Kalsoom, & Ali, 2025). Learning achievement, as an indicator of educational success, is affected by numerous factors such as teaching methods, access to academic support, peer interaction, and personal motivation (Shoaib, Rasool, & Iqbal, 2025b; Shoaib, Rasool, Iqbal, & Abdullah, 2025a). Gender disparities compound these influences, creating inequities in learning experiences and outcomes (Shoaib, Rasool, & Iqbal, 2025a, 2025c; Shoaib, Rasool, Zaman, & Ahmed, 2025; Shoaib, Shamsher, et al., 2025; Shoaib et al., 2025). However, measuring the extent and nature of these disparities has been challenging due to the lack of validated instruments that capture both gender-related differences and their effect on learning achievement (Shoaib, Iqbal, Rasool, & Abdullah, 2025; Shoaib, Kausar, Ali, & Abdullah, 2025; Shoaib, Tariq, Rasool, et al., 2025; Shoaib & Ullah, 2025; Shoaib, Waris, et al., 2025a).

Scale development and validation provide a methodological framework to address this gap (Shoaib, 2021; Shoaib, Tariq, & Iqbal, 2025a, 2025b; Shoaib & Ullah, 2019). By designing a

reliable and valid instrument, researchers systematically assess gender disparities and their relationship with learning outcomes (Shoib & Ullah, 2021a, 2021b). Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) allows for the statistical validation of the scale, ensuring that the items accurately reflect the underlying constructs and that the instrument generalized across different higher education contexts. In this context, the present study focuses on developing and validating a scale to measure gender disparity and its impact on learning achievement in higher education. By providing a psychometrically sound tool, the study aims to offer insights into the patterns and effects of gender disparities, enabling educators, policymakers, and researchers to implement targeted interventions that promote equitable learning environments and enhance academic success for all students. Hence, this study has been designed to develop and validate a scale of gender disparity and learning achievement in higher education using reliability test and confirmatory factor analysis.

The Data and Methods

This research paper has been based on quantitative study design having sample size more than 30. It has been conducted in one public sector university in the Punjab province. The students of BS 4 years constitute the population of the study. The sampling frame has been collected and a sample of 316 students have been selected using proportionate random sampling technique. The sample size has been proportionally allocated to each department of the faculty of the social sciences of the university. A cross-sectional survey has been conducted and structured questionnaire has been developed to collect quality data. The

measurement tool has been consisted of sections including gender disparity in enrolment, gender disparity in classroom, gender disparity in learning environment, gender disparity in communication, gender disparity in residential background, accessible resources, flexible instructional methods, supportive classroom climate, collaborative learning opportunities, equitable assessment methods, policy and institutional support, and culturally relevant teaching materials. Each variable has eight research items and overall 96 items constitute the complete scale. This tool has been pre-tested from 30 randomly selected students and an altitudinal scale of agreement and disagreement has been used. The reliability test has been confirmed by the value of Alpha (overall .939). The reliability test and confirmatory factor analysis has been done to confirm the factors of the measurement tool on the subject.

Results and Discussion

The reliability statistical test indicates that all the variables have significant value of Alpha i.e., .700 and above as it has been mentioned in Table 1. Similarly, the overall value of the scale has been calculated as .930 have 96 items in total. Hence, it has been confirmed that the scale is reliable. However, the validity of the instrument has also been measured by the group of research experts in the field of sociology of knowledge and sociology of gender. The validity of the instrument has been measured including face validity, internal and external validity, content validity, construct validity, criterion validity (predictive and concurrent), and discriminant validity.

Table 1 Reliability Test

Sr. No.	Variables	Codes	Items	Alpha-Value
i	Gender Disparity in Enrolment	GDIE	8	.728
ii	Gender Disparity in Classroom	GDIC	8	.718
iii	Gender Disparity in Learning Environment	GDIL	8	.720
iv	Gender Disparity in Communication	GDIN	8	.738
v	Gender Disparity in Residential Background	GDIR	8	.713
vi	Accessible Resources	ACRE	8	.741
vii	Flexible Instructional Methods	FLIM	8	.720
viii	Supportive Classroom Climate	SUCC	8	.733

ix	Collaborative Learning Opportunities	COLO	8	.735
x	Equitable Assessment Methods	EQAM	8	.730
xi	Policy and Institutional Support	PAIS	8	.748
xii	Culturally Relevant Teaching Materials	CRTM	8	.751
	Overall		96	.939

Table 2 CFA of the Variable Named as Gender Disparity in Enrolment

Sr. No.	Statement	Parameter Estimates	Standard Error	T Statistics	Prob. Level
i	There is a gender disparity in your class	0.293	0.064	4.575	0.000
ii	Females are unequal to male in enrollment	0.248	0.062	4.011	0.000
iii	Enrollment has been based on personal merit	0.254	0.059	4.322	0.000
iv	The enrollment process has been based on fairness	0.076	0.059	1.278	0.201
v	Female outclassed male students in enrollment	0.186	0.060	3.079	0.002
vi	Parents prefer for the enrollment of their females	0.511	0.058	8.890	0.000
vii	Education is better for females for mate selection	0.445	0.060	7.375	0.000
viii	Educating females results in better socialization of children	0.594	0.063	9.426	0.000

Table 2 revealed the CFA of the variable named as gender disparity in enrolment. The variable gender disparity in enrolment had been consisted on eight items/statements in total. As per the calculated value of probability level, seven items are confirmed and one item had not been confirmed i.e., iv. the enrollment process has been based on fairness. Hence, seven items or statements were confirmed and

used for further data analysis. It is worth to mention here that similar statements and review based items has also been used in previous studies conducted on the similar nature of subject in the field of sociology of education and sociology of gender (Shoab, Rasool, & Zaman, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c; Shoab, Rasool, Zaman, & Abdullah, 2025).

Table 3 CFA of the Variable Named as Gender Disparity in Classroom

Sr. No.	Statement	Parameter Estimates	Standard Error	T Statistics	Prob. Level
i	Classrooms are overcrowded with female	0.617	0.059	10.505	0.000
ii	Classroom activities are dominated by females students	0.597	0.055	10.912	0.000
iii	Classroom examples reinforce traditional gender roles	0.263	0.050	5.234	0.000
iv	Unequal teacher attention differentiate learning outcomes	0.231	0.058	3.973	0.000
v	Female students perform well in classroom	0.395	0.051	7.732	0.000
vi	Majority teachers listen female students carefully	0.176	0.057	3.083	0.002
vii	Female students actively participate in classroom	0.468	0.056	8.321	0.000
viii	Female teacher prefer female students to	0.078	0.064	1.226	0.220

sit in front of class

Table 3 revealed the CFA of the variable named as gender disparity in classroom. The variable gender disparity in classroom had been consisted on eight items/statements in total. As per the calculated value of probability level, seven items are confirmed and one item had not been confirmed i.e., viii. female teacher prefers female students to sit in front of class. Hence, seven items or statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. It

is important to mention here that similar items and systematic review based statements have also been used in previous researches conducted on the similar nature of subject in the field of sociology of education and sociology of gender (Shoaib, Rasool, & Iqbal, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c; Shoaib, Waris, et al., 2025a, 2025b; Shoaib, Waris, et al., 2025b).

Table 4 CFA of the Variable Named as Gender Disparity in Learning Environment

Sr. No.	Statement	Parameter Estimates	Standard Error	T Statistics	Prob. Level
i	Gender difference has been found in library activities	0.539	0.054	10.060	0.000
ii	Gender difference has been found in class learning	0.501	0.051	9.784	0.000
iii	Gender difference has been found to grasp the lecture	0.634	0.054	11.720	0.000
iv	Male and female students learn differently	0.293	0.058	5.049	0.000
v	Teacher focus on female students more as for male	0.200	0.054	3.713	0.000
vi	Female students have strong cognitive skills	0.121	0.054	2.225	0.026
vii	Female students have soft skills through learning	0.100	0.051	1.955	0.051
viii	Classrooms are more conducive for female students	0.199	0.054	3.676	0.000

Table 4 revealed the CFA of the variable named as gender disparity in learning environment. The variable gender disparity in learning environment had been consisted on eight items/statements in total. As per the calculated value of probability level, seven items are confirmed and one item had not been confirmed i.e., vii. female students have soft skills through learning. Hence, seven items or statements were confirmed and used for further

data analysis. It is note taking to mention here that similar research items and systematic review based statements have also been used in previous researches conducted on the similar nature of subject in the field of sociology of education and sociology of gender (Shoaib, Rasool, Iqbal, et al., 2025a, 2025b; Shoaib, Rasool, Kalsoom, et al., 2025).

Table 5 CFA of the Variable Named as Gender Disparity in Communication

Sr. No.	Statement	Parameter Estimates	Standard Error	T Statistics	Prob. Level
i	The gender of teacher contribute in communication of student	0.438	0.050	8.696	0.000
ii	The gender of student differentiate in communication	0.344	0.047	7.314	0.000
iii	Male and female students has different	0.480	0.051	9.460	0.000

	communication				
iv	Residential background differentiate in communication	0.319	0.053	6.061	0.000
v	Parental background differentiate in communication	0.328	0.054	6.121	0.000
vi	Male students have authoritative style of communication	0.290	0.050	5.843	0.000
vii	Females have submissive communication	0.347	0.051	6.794	0.000
viii	Communication of students has been linked with schooling	0.327	0.053	6.151	0.000

Table 5 revealed the CFA of the variable named as gender disparity in communication. The variable gender disparity in communication had been consisted on eight items/statements in total. As per the calculated value of probability level, eight items are confirmed. Hence, eight items or statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. Hence, seven items or statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. It

is note taking to mention here that similar research items and systematic review based statements have also been used in previous researches conducted on the similar nature of subject in the field of sociology of education and sociology of gender (Shoaib, Waris, et al., 2025c; Shoaib & Zaman, 2025; Shoaib, Zaman, et al., 2025).

Table 6 CFA of the Variable Named as Gender Disparity in Residential Backgrounds

Sr. No.	Statement	Parameter Estimates	Standard Error	T Statistics	Prob. Level
i	Residential backgrounds results in unequal grades	0.354	0.062	5.674	0.000
ii	The children of literate parents perform well	0.338	0.062	5.463	0.000
iii	Day scholar perform well as compared to hostelites	0.235	0.060	3.930	0.000
iv	Students of urban area perform well as rural area	0.429	0.069	6.232	0.000
v	Students from remote areas have less access to education	0.390	0.060	6.480	0.000
vi	Rural area have less educational facilities	0.423	0.061	6.926	0.000
vii	Students of urban area have advantages of higher education	0.217	0.065	3.345	0.001
viii	Students of rural backgrounds have less advantages of higher education	0.293	0.067	4.379	0.000

Table 6 revealed the CFA of the variable named as gender disparity in residential backgrounds. The variable gender disparity in residential backgrounds had been consisted on eight items/statements in total. As per the calculated value of probability level, eight items are confirmed. Hence, eight items or statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. Hence, seven items or statements were

confirmed and used for further data analysis. It is note taking to mention here that similar research items and systematic review based statements have also been used in previous researches conducted on the similar nature of subject in the field of sociology of education and sociology of gender (Shoaib, 2023a, 2023b).

Table 7 CFA of the Variable Named as Accessible Resources

Sr. No.	Statement	Parameter Estimates	Standard Error	T Statistics	Prob. Level
i	Unequal access has been provided to students by the teacher	0.111	0.060	1.855	0.064
ii	You have access to online forums	0.404	0.046	8.837	0.000
iii	You have access to educational databases	0.596	0.047	12.552	0.000
iv	You have access to audio, video material at the university	0.586	0.052	11.286	0.000
v	You have access to teaching resource	0.504	0.049	10.256	0.000
vi	You have access to university transport	0.512	0.053	9.709	0.000
vii	You have access to co-curricular activities	0.496	0.052	9.527	0.000
viii	You have access to software use during study	0.448	0.053	8.430	0.000

Table 7 revealed the CFA of the variable named as **accessible resources**. The variable **accessible resources** had been consisted on eight items/statements in total. As per the calculated value of probability level, seven items are confirmed and one item had not been confirmed i.e., i. unequal access has been provided to students by the teacher. Hence, seven items or statements were confirmed and

used for further data analysis. Hence, seven items or statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. It is note taking to mention here that similar research items and systematic review based statements have also been used in previous researches conducted on the similar nature of subject in the field of sociology of education and sociology of gender (Shoaib, 2024a, 2024c).

Table 8 CFA of the Variable Named as Flexible Instructional Methods

Sr. No.	Statement	Parameter Estimates	Standard Error	T Statistics	Prob. Level
i	Male teacher interact with students equally	0.335	0.050	6.708	0.000
ii	Female teacher interact with student equally	0.275	0.050	5.484	0.000
iii	You participate in classroom discussion	0.467	0.048	9.708	0.000
iv	You listen lecture carefully	0.554	0.051	10.831	0.000
v	You are active participant in debate	0.573	0.049	11.769	0.000
vi	You are active learner student in the classroom	0.551	0.048	11.433	0.000
vii	You ask the question in classroom	0.657	0.050	13.270	0.000
viii	You learn from student centered classroom	0.596	0.053	11.327	0.000

Table 8 revealed the CFA of the variable named as **flexible instructional methods**. The variable **flexible instructional methods** had been consisted on eight items/statements in total. As per the calculated value of probability level, eight items are confirmed. Hence, eight items or statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. Hence, seven items or

statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. It is note taking to mention here that similar research items and systematic review based statements have also been used in previous researches conducted on the similar nature of subject in the field of sociology of education and sociology of gender (Shoaib, 2024b, 2024d).

Table 9 CFA of the Variable Named as Supportive Classroom Climate

Sr. No.	Statement	Parameter Estimates	Standard Error	T Statistics	Prob. Level
i	You feel safe in the classroom	0.652	0.051	12.895	0.000
ii	You practice appropriate discipline in classroom	0.478	0.043	11.249	0.000
iii	You believe in positive students outcomes	0.571	0.041	14.035	0.000
iv	You have warn communication with others	0.443	0.047	9.397	0.000
v	You have accessibility of career content	0.543	0.048	11.284	0.000
vi	You have the student of inclusive environment	0.373	0.044	8.556	0.000
vii	You are emotionally attached with the classroom	0.391	0.052	7.575	0.000
viii	You accept the social climate of classroom	0.465	0.046	10.192	0.000

Table 9 revealed the CFA of the variable named as **supportive classroom climate**. The variable **supportive classroom climate** had been consisted on eight items/statements in total. As per the calculated value of probability level, eight items are confirmed. Hence, eight items or statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. Hence, seven items or

statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. It is note taking to mention here that similar research items and systematic review based statements have also been used in previous researches conducted on the similar nature of subject in the field of sociology of education and sociology of gender (Shoaib, 2024e; Shoaib, Ali, & Abbas, 2024).

Table 10 CFA of the Variable Named as Collaborative Learning Opportunities

Sr. No.	Statement	Parameter Estimates	Standard Error	T Statistics	Prob. Level
i	You study in your class group	0.518	0.054	9.589	0.000
ii	You prefer to write study work in group	0.536	0.050	10.804	0.000
iii	You learn from your peer group at the university	0.525	0.046	11.348	0.000
iv	You are the active member in the group	0.471	0.048	9.786	0.000
v	You perform collaborative learning activities	0.551	0.044	12.462	0.000
vi	You articulate your knowledge in group	0.495	0.041	12.096	0.000
vii	You demonstrate in group activity in front of others	0.516	0.047	10.923	0.000
viii	You develop your metacognitive skill during group study	0.560	0.047	11.946	0.000

Table 10 revealed the CFA of the variable named as **collaborative learning opportunities**. The variable **collaborative learning opportunities** had been consisted on eight items/statements in total. As per the calculated value of probability level, eight items are confirmed. Hence, eight items or statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. Hence, seven items or statements were

confirmed and used for further data analysis. It is note taking to mention here that similar research items and systematic review based statements have also been used in previous researches conducted on the similar nature of subject in the field of sociology of education and sociology of gender (Ahmed, Shoaib, & Zaman, 2025; Ali, Shoaib, & Kausar, 2025; Shoaib, 2025b).

Table 11 CFA of the Variable Named as Equitable Assessment Methods

Sr. No.	Statement	Parameter Estimates	Standard Error	T Statistics	Prob. Level
i	Your assessment has been based on transparently	0.358	0.063	5.718	0.000
ii	Multiple assessment method has been used in your class	0.339	0.062	5.474	0.000
iii	Teachers use standardize assessment methods	0.243	0.060	4.050	0.000
iv	Your evaluation has been based on merit	0.425	0.069	6.187	0.000
v	Your assessment has been done on time	0.381	0.060	6.332	0.000
vi	Your assessment has been accessed by sessional work	0.419	0.061	6.843	0.000
vii	Your assessment has been based on presentation skills	0.212	0.065	3.254	0.001
viii	Your assessment is based on exams in the semester	0.309	0.067	4.642	0.000

Table 11 revealed the CFA of the variable named as **equitable assessment methods**. The variable **equitable assessment methods** had been consisted on eight items/statements in total. As per the calculated value of probability level, eight items are confirmed. Hence, eight items or statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. Hence, seven items or statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. It is note taking to mention here

that similar research items and systematic review based statements have also been used in previous researches conducted on the similar nature of subject in the field of sociology of education and sociology of gender (Shoaib, 2025a; Shoaib, Ahmed, & Iqbal, 2025; Shoaib, Ahmed, Iqbal, & Abdullah, 2025; Shoaib, Iqbal, & Iftikhar, 2025; Muhammad Shoaib, Shamraiz Iqbal, et al., 2025; Muhammad Shoaib, Noreena Kausar, et al., 2025).

Table 12 CFA of the Variable Named as Policy and Institutional Support

Sr. No.	Statement	Parameter Estimates	Standard Error	T Statistics	Prob. Level
i	You practice standardize rules in the university	0.250	0.051	4.926	0.000
ii	Physical facilities have been provided to you	0.498	0.049	10.227	0.000
iii	Software have been provided to you in the university	0.543	0.049	11.180	0.000
iv	Transport facilities have been provided to you	0.290	0.056	5.200	0.000
v	University resources have been equally distributed	0.536	0.048	11.072	0.000
vi	You have full institutional support for your study	0.534	0.045	11.823	0.000
vii	University implement different policies as per routine	0.518	0.045	11.602	0.000
viii	Your university focus on smooth educational activities	0.539	0.048	11.187	0.000

Table 12 revealed the CFA of the variable named as **policy and institutional support**. The variable **policy and institutional support** had been consisted on eight items/statements in total. As per the calculated value of probability

level, eight items are confirmed. Hence, eight items or statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. Hence, seven items or statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. It is note taking to mention here

that similar research items and systematic review based statements have also been used in previous researches conducted on the similar nature of subject in the field of sociology of

education and sociology of gender (Shoaib, Ahmed, & Usmani, 2025a, 2025b; Shoaib, Ahmed, Zaman, & Abdullah, 2025).

Table 13 CFA of the Variable Named as Culturally Relevant Teaching Materials

Sr. No.	Statement	Parameter Estimates	Standard Error	T Statistics	Prob. Level
i	Your study material has been based on cultural codes	0.500	0.050	9.912	0.000
ii	Cultural values has been practiced in classroom	0.505	0.047	10.795	0.000
iii	Dress code has been implemented	0.411	0.048	8.567	0.000
iv	Cultural values are very important in the classroom	0.537	0.049	10.938	0.000
v	Gender based study culture has been practiced	0.265	0.049	5.359	0.000
vi	Students have freedom to practice cultural values	0.446	0.044	10.211	0.000
vii	Students respects the teachers	0.416	0.048	8.603	0.000
viii	Each student has respect in classroom in front of others	0.490	0.049	9.899	0.000

Table 13 revealed the CFA of the variable named as **culturally relevant teaching materials**. The variable **culturally relevant teaching materials** had been consisted on eight items/statements in total. As per the calculated value of probability level, eight items are confirmed. Hence, eight items or statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. Hence, seven items or statements were confirmed and used for further data analysis. It is note taking to mention here that similar research items and systematic review based statements have also been used in previous researches conducted on the similar nature of subject in the field of sociology of education and sociology of gender (Shoaib, Ali, Iqbal, & Abdullah, 2025; Shoaib, Ali, & Kausar, 2025; Shoaib & Bashir, 2025).

Conclusion

This study concludes that the development and validation of a scale to measure gender disparity and learning achievement is essential for understanding and addressing inequities in higher education. The use of a psychometrically sound instrument, validated through confirmatory factor analysis, ensures that gender-related differences and their impact on academic outcomes are accurately captured.

Findings from the scale provide actionable insights for educators, administrators, and policymakers, enabling them to identify areas of inequality, design targeted interventions, and promote equitable learning opportunities. Ultimately, the validated scale serves as a robust tool to support evidence-based strategies aimed at reducing gender disparities and enhancing learning achievement for all students in higher education institutions.

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